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epidemiological survey
design and clinical data.
JIP COVRIN WP3**

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EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SURVEY DESIGN AND CLINICAL DATA OF SARS-COV-2 IN PETS

1. Introduction

COVRIN aims to integrate research by One Health EJP partner institutes on the topics of SARS-CoV-2 emergence, risk assessment and preparedness. The project has two main operational objectives: (i) to identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV-2, and (ii) to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV-2. To achieve these objectives, integrative research activities are focused on four topics: (i) research on detection of SARS-CoV-2 in animal species and the environment; (ii) research on SARS-CoV-2 molecular and biological characterization; (iii) SARS-CoV-2 surveillance and risk assessment, focussed on the animal human interface; and (iv) coronavirus preparedness. The overall aim of the COVRIN project is to generate and share data of these integrative research activities, in order to increase the preparedness for future coronavirus outbreaks.

2. Description of the task

WP3 aims to integrate the currently fragmented data from sampling of animals and the environment across partner countries, into an aligned One-Health surveillance system for SARS-CoV-2 that is based on data from the three components (i.e. humans, animals, and the environment), as well as the different sectors therein (e.g. pets, livestock, wildlife).

This report describes the outcomes of Subtask 3.3.1 “Conduction of an epidemiological survey to analysis the transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in exposed pets” which is part of Task 3.3 “Risk factors for virus transmission” (WP3).

Many uncertainties about the behaviour of SARS-CoV-2 persist, and understanding all the keys of this epidemic requires an interdisciplinary One Health approach spanning the human and animal health sectors. The closest coexistence between people and animals occurs in large cities. This subtask aims to collect epidemiology and laboratory data of pets that have coexisted with family groups affected by SARS-CoV-2 in areas of high population density and high disease incidence by **designing an epidemiological survey and sampling protocol templates for pets to facilitate the collection of data with the purpose of integrating this information from different countries.**

3. Description of the work

A conceptual assessment of the epidemiological survey and sampling design was carried out in a region of Spain with a high prevalence of SARS-Cov2 infection. In order to collect epidemiological and clinical data on family groups affected by the disease and their pets, a network of veterinary clinics has been created to provide sampling points for the pets. The SARS-Cov2 affected family groups include both hospital health workers and non-health workers pet owners in order to evaluate heavily and typically exposed pets (informed through the vet clinic network). The health workers recruited for this study are

affiliated with two public hospitals that collaborated with our group through two national projects (EPICO and SANICOVID).

Each owner completed a consent form, an epidemiological questionnaire online or on paper, and a confidential health questionnaire. For each pet, these three documents, as well as samples (oral and nasal swabs and blood), are collected.

Surveys were statistically analysed and samples were analysed by PCR and ELISA at the CISA (INIA-CSIC) laboratory.

3.1.) Design and conduction of an epidemiological survey to analysis the transmission of SARSCov-2

The epidemiological survey was based on a questionnaire for dogs and cats that was divided into eight sections:

1. General information: Identification of owner, pet date etc
2. Household information: Number of householdes, children, profession, number of bedrooms..
3. SARS-COV 2 status of householders: PCR /ELISA/Antigens positive test and date (*).
4. Pet data: age, specie, breed, gender, weight.
5. Environment and habits of the pet: outdoor, indoor, park visits..
6. If your pet sleeps at home (conditional section): in the bed, box...
7. External contacts and food: contact with external people or animals, type of food.
8. Health and clinical information: Symptoms, duration, vaccination card..

(*)Furthermore, each owner filled out a confidential form detailing the date of their positive Sars-cov2 test, the positive tests of other cohabitants, and their familial relationship to them. Public health hospitals collected this information while maintaining data confidentiality.

Participants in the study could choose between a link to the survey and a paper survey.

LINK: <https://forms.gle/6rvQhGoLBawqP9Pt9>

The survey was created with Google Questionaries, which allows the designer to automatically download completed surveys in excel format online.

For database and statistical analyses of questionnaire responses, Excel and SPSS v.23 were used (frequency distributions, chi-square statistics for two by two contingency tables to obtain measures of association, and the statistical significance of such associations,...)

3.2) Sampling exposed pets doing the diagnosis of infections with SARS-Cov-2 by PCR and ELISA.

When a pet owner visits a health center and tests positive for SARS-CoV-2, they must be isolated, and we provide a sampling kit and protocols for oral and nasal swabbing of their pet for the antigen test (PCR). When the pet owner is not infected, they can bring their pet to the veterinarian for a COVID antibody test using a blood sample (ELISA).

The purpose of the sampling protocol is to make it easier for the owner to obtain a sample of their pet and to obtain samples during the owner's contagious period, which will allow for an earlier, more standardized, and more effective test. The protocol for blood sampling was destined for animal health professionals.

PROTOCOL FOR SAMPLING PETS

SAMPLING ORAL AND NASAL

Swabs to collect nasal and oral fluids. The sampling kit includes the following items:

- Two swabs inside sealed package
- Two plastics tubes/ependorf with a solution (PBS)
- A zipper lock bag
- Authorization form to complete by the pet owner

TEST KIT CONTENTS:

Step 1

- Sample dogs when there are no food particles in their mouths
- Write the pet's identification on the exterior of the tube and bag
- Every animal requires two swabs, oral and nasal (tubes have a blue or green sticker to distinguish), to small dogs and cats requiring only oral swabs.
- Please, fully wash your hands before taking the sample.

Step 2

- Peel open the swab packaging when you are ready to use.
- Take out the swap taking care not to touch the sampling end.

Step 3 NASAL SAMPLE FOR MEDIUM and LARGE DOGS (GREEN TUBE) ●

- When you are ready to use the swab, peel open the packaging.
- Take out the swab being careful not to touch the end used for sampling.
- Carefully insert the swab into the nostril until you feel a slight resistance. Roll the swab gently and out slowly. Carefully remove the swab from the nostril.
- Open the plastic tube and introduce the swab inside.
- Click the plastic tube's cap into place before inserting it into the zip lock bag.
- **Store the zip lock bag on the freezer (-4°C) until it is to be collected for laboratory analysis.**

Step 4. ORAL SAMPLE FOR DOGS, CATS AND FERRETS (BLUE TUBE) ●

- When you are ready to use the swab, peel open the packaging.
- Take out the swab being careful not to touch the end used for sampling.
- Place swab between the cheek and gum after lifting the lip.
- Roll the swab between the cheek and gum for 15 seconds, letting the lip fall and applying firm pressure to the outside of the muzzle.
- Open the plastic tube and introduce the swab inside.
- Click the plastic tube's cap into place before inserting it into the zip lock bag.
- **Store the zip lock bag on the freezer (-4°C) until it is to be collected for laboratory analysis.**

LABELLING THE ZIP LOCK BAG AND COMPLETING THE ONLINE EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SURVEY

- *Instructions for the specific identification by each institution*
- **PLEASE COMPLETE THE ONLINE SURVEY AVAILABLE AT**
<https://forms.gle/eWuEUqxqwUMz4f4GA>

AUTHORIZATION FORM TO COMPLETE BY THE PET OWNER

Please complete the authorization form and introduce into the zip lock bag.

TAKING THE BLOOD SAMPLE FOR ANALYSIS

- Two blood tubes without any additives inside are required.
- The smallest sample amount is 1 ml. The veterinarian collects blood samples and puts them in the tube.
- Leave the tube an hour at room temperature.
- Store the tube in the refrigerator at 4 °C for 12 hours (overnight).
- Centrifuge the tube for 10 minutes at 2500 rpm.
- Remove the serum with a pipette, place it in the other tube, and discard the blood pellet.
- Use the pet's identification to label the serum tube.

Instructions for the specific identification

- The tube containing the serum should be kept in the freezer (-4°C) until it is to be collected for laboratory analysis.

4. The procedure for data collection and integration

The conceptual assessment of the epidemiological survey and sampling design was carried out in a region of Spain with a high prevalence of SARS-Cov2 infection (The Community of Madrid) during 2020-2022.

Data for epidemiological and clinical studies were taken from sixty family units along with their household pets. On each pet, an epidemiological questionnaire was carried out in addition to the collection of samples (oral and nasal swabs, feces, and blood). RRT-PCR and ELISA were the methods that were used to analyze the samples. Five cats presented antibodies, out of a total of 55 pets tested (there were 17 cats and 38 dogs). This seroprevalence is consistent with the findings of other authors in cats from severely affected areas such as Italy, Brazil, and France. The preliminary results were presented at the biannual International Meeting on Emerging Diseases and Surveillance (IMED) 2021. The study was selected for publication in the International Journal of Infectious Diseases (IJID): A. Mendez, M.A. Jiménez-Clavero, C. Calvo, E. Pérez-Ramírez, J. Fernández-Pinero, F. Llorente, T. Sainz, P. Aguilera-Sepúlveda, S. Alcolea, L. Escolano, C. Cano, I. Novoa, A. De la Torre, I. Iglesias (2022) SARS-CoV-2 in pets of infected family groups in a severely affected region in Spain, International Journal of Infectious Diseases, Volume 116: S25. ISSN 1201-9712. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2021.12.059>

Currently, we are collaborating with another research group at the University of Alfonso X in Madrid. This other group has conducted tests on approximately 70 pets that belonged to SARS-Cov2-infected owners and found a comparable percentage of positive results. We are standardizing the epidemiological information that is provided to pet owners in order to increase the number of animals that participate in the survey's collection of epidemiological data in the same region. The findings will allow for the identification of potential risk factors for the transmission of SARS-Cov-2 in the human-pet interface, which can be used to feed mathematical modelling and risk analysis, and will contribute to the completion of subtask 3.3.2. Currently, the article detailing all of the findings is being written.

The developed work framework will be shared with other institutions participating in WP 3 in order to increase the study's epidemiological information and facilitate data integration.

To replicate the study in a different region, it is necessary to have contact with public health sectors and the ability to collect and analyze samples. The study flow diagram is summarized in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Study flow diagram of subtask 3.3.1.

PS04.03 (285)

SARS-CoV-2 in pets of infected family groups in a severely affected region in Spain

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Purpose

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused an unprecedented health crisis with devastating effects. Current evidence suggests that SARS-CoV-2 could have an animal origin. Many uncertainties about the behaviour of the virus still persist, and understanding all the keys of this epidemic requires an interdisciplinary One Health approach spanning the human and animal health sectors. The closest coexistence between people and animals occurs in large cities. This study aims to identify the epidemiology (infection rate, risk habits, etc...) and evolution of the disease in pets that have coexisted during the confinement with family groups affected by the disease in areas of high population density and high disease incidence, i.e. Madrid.

Methods & Materials

A network of veterinary clinics was created to provide sampling points for the pets. The family groups included both health workers from the collaborating hospitals and affected pet owners informed through the network of clinics.

Results

Epidemiological and clinical data were collected from 60 family groups and their pets. An epidemiological questionnaire and sample collection (oral and nasal swabs, faeces and blood) were carried out on each pet. The samples were analyzed by RRT-PCR and ELISA. Of the 55 pets analysed (17 cats and 38 dogs), 5 cats presented antibodies. This seroprevalence is in agreement with that shown by Patterson et al, 2020 in cats in Italy in highly affected areas.

Conclusion

This study intends to extend the knowledge of the epidemiology and evolution of the disease in pets.

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4. Bibliography

- Hosie, M. J., Hofmann-Lehmann, R., Hartmann, K., Egberink, H., Truyen, U., Addie, D. D., ... & Möstl, K. (2021). Anthropogenic infection of cats during the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic. *Viruses*, 13(2), 185.
- Schulz C. et al., (2021) SARS-CoV-2–specific antibodies in domestic cats during first COVID-19 wave, Europe. *Emerging Infectious Diseases*. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2712.211252>, https://wwwnc.cdc.gov/eid/article/27/12/21-1252_article
- Guidelines for Working with Free-Ranging Wild Mammals in the Era of the COVID-19 Pandemic. OIE
- Decaro, N., & Buonavoglia, C. (2008). An update on canine coronaviruses: viral evolution and pathobiology. *Veterinary microbiology*, 132(3-4), 221-234.
- Greger, M. (2007). The human/animal interface: emergence and resurgence of zoonotic infectious diseases. *Critical reviews in microbiology*, 33(4), 243-299.
- Bosco-Lauth, A. M., Hartwig, A. E., Porter, S. M., Gordy, P. W., Nehring, M., Byas, A. D., ... & Bowen, R. A. (2020). Pathogenesis, transmission and response to re-exposure of SARS-CoV-2 in domestic cats. *BioRxiv*.
- Preventative Measures regarding SARS-CoV-2 and Ferrets in the UK December 2020 . APHA
- Hammer, A. S., Quaade, M. L., Rasmussen, T. B., Fonager, J., Rasmussen, M., Mundbjerg, K., ... & Bøtner, A. (2021). SARS-CoV-2 transmission between mink (*Neovison vison*) and humans, Denmark. *Emerging infectious diseases*, 27(2), 547.
- E.I. Patterson, G. Elia, A. Grassi, A. Giordano, C. Desario, M. Medardo, S.L. Smith, E.R. Anderson, T. Prince, G.T. Patterson, E. Lorusso, M.S. Lucente, G. Lanave, S. Lauzi, U. Bonfanti, A. Stranieri, V. Martella, F. Solari Basano, V.R. Barrs, A.D. Radford, U. Agrimi, G. L. Hughes, S. Paltrinieri, N. Decaro *bioRxiv* 2020.07.21.214346; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.07.21.214346>
- Shi, J., Wen, Z., Zhong, G., Yang, H., Wang, C., Huang, B., ... & Bu, Z. (2020). Susceptibility of ferrets, cats, dogs, and other domesticated animals to SARS–coronavirus 2. *Science*, 368(6494), 1016-1020.
- SARS-CoV-2 neutralizing serum antibodies in cats: a serological investigation, Qiang Zhang, Huajun Zhang, Kun Huang, Yong Yang, Xianfeng Hui, Jindong Gao, Xinglin He, Chengfei Li, Wenxiao Gong, Yufei Zhang, Cheng Peng, Xiaoxiao Gao,